

Technical Report: Bibliographic Survey

Human Perceptions Meet AI Analysis: A Usability Evaluation of Climate Conference Websites

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1. Abstract

This technical report documents the bibliographic survey conducted to establish the theoretical and methodological foundations of the study. The review was structured to ensure the relevance, quality, and traceability of the works selected to support the analysis of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) applications in usability evaluation, with particular focus on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) contexts.

2. Research Question

The central question guiding the bibliographic search was:

"In what manner do Generative Artificial Intelligences and real users converge or diverge in the evaluation of the usability of the COP30 website? Additionally, how do GAI evaluations of COP29 and COP30 compare, and what do these findings indicate for Human-Computer Interaction practices?"

3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

3.1 Inclusion Criteria

- Studies addressing GAI applications in usability evaluation
- Studies on automated heuristic evaluation methods
- Studies related to Human-Computer Interaction and user experience

3.2 Exclusion Criteria

- Incomplete texts or those without methodological detail
- Studies not directly addressing evaluative methods
- Duplicates across databases

4. Databases Consulted

Searches were conducted in five primary databases:

Database	URL
IEEE Xplore	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org
Scopus	https://www.scopus.com

ACM Digital Library	https://dl.acm.org
SciELO	https://scielo.br
Google Scholar	https://scholar.google.com/

5. Search Strings

The following descriptors were used as search terms: Generative AI; Usability Evaluation; Automated Heuristic Evaluation; and Human-Computer Interaction. Search strings were adapted to the syntax and field conventions of each database, combining the descriptors through Boolean operators (AND/OR) applied to title, abstract, and keyword fields.

6. Screening Results

The table below summarizes the number of records identified, screened, and selected at each stage of the review process:

Database	Initial Results	After Title/Abstract Screening	After Full Reading
IEEE Xplore	48	5	0
Scopus	74	16	4
ACM Digital Library	45	11	5
SciELO	15	2	0
Google Scholar	89	18	4
Total (raw)	271	52	13
Total (deduplicated)	210	52	13

No studies retrieved from IEEE Xplore or SciELO met the inclusion criteria after full-text reading.

7. Selected References

- Alsadi, A. and Miller, D. (2023). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence language model ChatGPT on the user experience. *IJTIM*.
- Araújo, M. F. B. et al. (2024). Combinando inteligência artificial generativa e inspeção humana. *IHC 2024*.
- Bleichner, A. and Hermansson, N. (2023). Investigating the usefulness of a generative AI when designing user interfaces. *Uppsala University*.
- Borges, J. M. and Araújo, R. D. (2024). Experiences and challenges of a redesign process with AI support. *IHC 2024*.

- Fischer, M. and Lanquillon, C. (2024). Evaluation of generative AI-assisted software design and engineering. Springer.
- Hornbæk, K. and Hertzum, M. (2017). Technology acceptance and user experience. ACM TOCHI.
- Ivory, M. Y. and Hearst, M. A. (2001). The state of the art in automating usability evaluation. ACM Computing Surveys.
- Kuric, E. et al. (2025). Systematic literature review of automation and AI in usability issue detection. Scopus.
- Li, D. (2024). Exploration of user experience design optimization. Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences.
- Miraz, M. H. et al. (2017). Multilingual website usability analysis. CoRR.
- Serra, L. et al. (2015). Accessibility evaluation of e-government mobile applications in Brazil. Procedia Computer Science.
- White, J. et al. (2023). A prompt pattern catalog to enhance prompt engineering with ChatGPT. arXiv.
- Nielsen, J. (1994). Heuristic evaluation.